

**THE ROLE OF WATER IN WOMEN AND CRIME:
A BLUE HUMANITIES READING OF WATERSCAPES IN
DAMYANTI BISWAS' THE BLUE BAR
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ABSTRACT:

Blue humanities is an interdisciplinary field that explores the relationship between water, human life, culture, history and literature. It portrays water as a symbolic element of memory, trauma, renewal or transformation. It reveals that watery spaces expose women's insecurity and the violence rooted in society. The paper applies the theory in the analysis of *The Blue Bar* (2023) by Damyanti Biswas, to examine how water has a deep and symbolic connection with a female character named Tara. As a bar dancer, Tara faces a lot of pressure in her life and struggles to survive in the dangerous urban landscape of Mumbai city. She carries emotional wounds from her past caused by bitter experiences of exploitation and insecurity. However, she constantly tries to rebuild herself by finding moments of stability even in chaotic surroundings. Water helps her to heal by keeping her mind steady and offering her a brief moment of peace and focus. Thus, it becomes a source of calmness and mental clarity for Tara. Just as every coin has two sides, watery spaces also have negative aspects that are portrayed in *The Blue Bar*. The paper aims to highlight the role of water as a witness to crime, since the novel includes crime scenes set near coastal areas. It attempts to reveal how coastal lines and beaches possess the trace of violence in the novel.

KEYWORDS:

Blue humanities, *The Blue Bar*, Damyanti Biswas, Water, Crime.

Crime thriller is a genre that combines elements of crime stories with the suspense of thrillers. The primary goal is to create feelings of suspense, surprise and anxiety for the audience. It focuses on criminal acts like murder, kidnapping, serial killing and conspiracy. Lee Child, a British author famous for creating the Jack Reacher series of crime thriller novels, says “Crime fiction is about the effect of a crime on a family or a community” (Bidinotto, 2011). In Indian Writing in English, the crime thriller genre exposes India’s social injustice, cultural tensions and power structures. Unlike many Western thrillers, Indian crime thrillers place significant emphasis on social realism alongside suspense. In recent times, the term Indian crime fiction in English is applicable to the work of Indian authors residing in the nation along with the writers of diaspora. Contemporary Indian crime thriller writers in English include Bhaskar Chattopadhyay, Anuja Chauhan, Ashwin Sanghi, Piyush Jha, Damyanti Biswas and RV Raman. The paper analyses Damyanti Biswas’ *The Blue Bar* through the lens of blue humanities to reveal how water and watery spaces shape the story and the characters.

Blue humanities, a phrase coined by literary scholar Steve Mentz in 2009, is an emerging field that treats the ocean as both a material and social entity. It explores themes like interconnectedness, exploration, exploitation and conservation through lenses of humanities and sciences. In a review, Julia Stryker says,

“By definition expansive, multi-modal, and dis-orienting, the blue humanities operate as both a big-tent intellectual discourse and a way of thinking... Emerging from literary studies, the label corrals and directs an observable, cross-disciplinary surge of interest in studying water and humanity’s relationship to it, arguably underway well before the turn of the century but certainly at a pitch in volume thereafter. Capacious and fluid, the blue humanities intend to rejoin “compartmentalized” developments like coastal studies, studies of the Middle Passage, literary studies’ turn to maritime work, and the climate-change-driven explosion in scientific investigations of watery ecosystems of all types. The Blue humanities refine and

relate scholarship rather than proscribe subjects or approaches beyond the very broad subject and deliberate encouragement of creative methods and outputs (2024).”

The field emerged in the twenty-first century due to the impact of climate change and a growing awareness of the ocean’s cultural significance. It has expanded recently to include various disciplines such as Blue Culture Studies, Maritime History, Marine Biology and Coastal Sociology. It foregrounds water as a central element in human history and cultural production.

Water is a natural element that is essential for life. It is a transparent, tasteless and odourless substance that covers 70% of earth’s surface. It helps to regulate the temperature of the earth and supports various ecosystems. It is necessary for daily activities like drinking, cooking, cleaning and agriculture. In literature, water often works as a symbol of life, movement, change, memory or healing. Margaret Atwood in her *The Penelopiad* (2005) says,

“Water does not resist. Water flows. When you plunge your hand into it, all you feel is a caress. Water is not a solid wall, it will not stop you. But water always goes where it wants to go, and nothing in the end can stand against it. Water is patient. Dripping water wears away a stone. Remember that, my child. Remember you are half water. If you can’t go through an obstacle, go around it. Water does.” (p. 43)

The theory of blue humanities illustrates water not just as a physical substance but a central force that shapes human culture, history, identity and imagination. It connects the female body to water and argues that they are not separate entities but they mutually influence each other. The paper analyses the role of water in consoling the mind of a female character in Damyanti Biswas’ *The Blue Bar*.

The Blue Bar by Damyanti Biswas, published in the year 2023, is a crime thriller novel that revolves around the crime scenes

that take place near coastal areas. Tara, the female protagonist of the novel, is a dancer in a bar named Blue Bar. Wearing a blue-sequined saree, she disappears from Mumbai in the opening chapter leaving her lover Arnav, a police constable, to struggle with confusion, longing and the pain of uncertainty. Years later, Arnav becomes the Inspector in the Malwani Police Station. He is deeply involved in a serial killing case of young women with blue sequins on their bodies, which becomes more personal as he is suspected to have a connection with Tara's disappearance. After fourteen years, Tara comes back to Mumbai. She joins in the same Blue Bar as both a choreographer and dancer to earn money for her secret daughter's schooling. When Pia, the daughter of Tara, is kidnapped, Tara reveals to Arnav that Pia is his own daughter. She also admits that this hidden truth forces her to leave Arnav years ago. With the help of other officers, Arnav not only rescues his daughter but also unmasks the serial killer, leading to an interesting climax.

Filled with various themes, the novel throws light on blue humanities by exploring the relationship between a woman and water. Tara, whose real name is Noyontara Mondal, has a strong and meaningful relationship with water. Her disappearance from Mumbai can be compared to the movement of water. She goes out of visibility like water moving away and flowing into different hidden places. This act of Tara makes her escape from the dangerous situations and oppressive forces. Just as water changes its direction and adapts to new surroundings, Tara is forced to get out of her bar life in Mumbai and moves to Lucknow to secure the future of her unborn child. Her life changes from being a bar dancer to a mother. The author says, "Tara was a teenager when she fell pregnant, practically a child herself and she'd not only given birth and raised a child, she'd made an entire life in a new place. She was here, trying to build their child's future" (Biswas, 2023, p. 259). Tara's return after fourteen years into the life of Arnav and the city symbolises renewal. The ability of the water to cleanse the past and reset new surroundings is compared to Tara's fresh start in a new chapter of her life. This

presents water as a symbol of rebirth, renewal and hope of a fresh beginning.

In *The Blue Bar*, water often appears during moments of stress or fear for Tara. It serves as a source of comfort and acuity during her hardships. At her thirteen, Tara was forced to join the Blue Bar as a dancer due to her father's alcoholism. Her life seems to be incomplete without proper education and meaningful relationships. However, water helps Tara forget all these things by offering her short moments of mental peace. Zoya, the caretaker of Tara, says "You never sleep without a bath" (Biswas, 2023, p.114). The article by Lacey Muinos and Jessica Migala states, "Baths may evoke a greater sense of calm and tranquility" (2025). Bathing or being near water gives Tara brief calm, clarity and emotional grounding in the middle of her chaotic life. Water not only removes the dirt on Tara's body but also clears the painful memories and harsh experiences of her life as a bar dancer from her mind.

When Tara's daughter Pia is kidnapped, water becomes a quiet space where she can breathe and regain strength. The author says, "He knew she would take a bath – the one thing that steadied her" (Biswas, 2023, p. 259). Water keeps her mind steady and makes her act wise in traumatic situations. It gives her a sense of control over herself when everything around her feels unstable. The author also says, "Tara had locked herself in the bathroom after she finished with the kitchen chores. She'd not emerged for more than an hour" (Biswas, 2023, p. 271). This act of Tara reflects her need for emotional escape and healing. She prefers being near water rather than being with people like Arnav. By staying inside for more than an hour, she seeks comfort in the presence of water. It helps her calm her mind and temporarily makes her forget the trauma of her daughter's kidnapping. Water becomes a force that soothes her inner wounds, washing away the emotional burden she carries. Thus, water can be viewed as a symbolic element that has a close relationship with Tara by shaping her emotions and experiences.

Water also functions as a silent witness to crime scenes that happen near coastal areas or beaches in the novel. It holds traces of violence that some characters try to hide. Coastal mangroves and watery spaces in the novel become sites where bodies and evidences are hidden. The author says,

“It wasn’t entirely uncommon to find dead bodies washed up on the beaches and in the surrounding mangrove forests, though this was the first time in Arnav’s three years posted at the Malwani station that he’d heard of a body buried at a site. Mumbai’s gangs disposed of their ghatias and bhaiyas, troublesome peers and victims alike, in the coastal mangroves. They expected the tide to carry the bodies out into the waters. Sometimes, they miscalculated the moods of the sea, and decomposed remains turned up on the local beaches” (Biswas, 2023, p. 7).

Mumbai’s criminal gangs use coastal mangroves as dumping grounds for murder victims. Since the coastal mangroves are dense with waterways, they consider the place to be safe to dump the dead bodies. They also depend on the tide to carry the bodies into the sea, which removes the evidence of their crimes. The authors of “Why Are We Missing Aquatic Murders?” article say, “Identifying, investigating, and prosecuting aquatic abuse and murder can be challenging. Aquatic scenes can be large, uncontrollable, and difficult to access. The water can hide, damage, and move corpses and other evidence hundreds of kilometers” (Zaferes and Hill, 2024). However, the sea is not always predictable due to its changing moods. When the tide does not flow as per the expectations of the criminals, the decomposed bodies they tried to hide come back to the local beaches, revealing the violence that the criminals committed. Water tides have their own moods that cannot be controlled by human beings. Thus, water serves as both witness to the crime and the force that reveals the truth.

Damyanti Biswas in her *The Blue Bar* clearly illustrates the complex relationship between woman and water through the lens of

Blue Humanities. The paper shows that water functions both as a physical element and a symbolic force in the novel. It shapes the emotional and psychological ideas of the protagonist, Tara. The shifting nature of water, which is connected with Tara's disappearance and reappearance, represents the renewal of her life. Water acts as a soothing element that steadies her mind during her hardships, offering her a brief moment to escape from the present trauma. It also becomes a medium that records the criminal activity of Mumbai's criminal gangs. Thus, the paper illustrates the relationship between Tara and water through Damyanti Biswas' *The Blue Bar* along with highlighting the darker side of watery spaces.

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